

As we enter the winter months, DDI activity continues apace. We have a lot of interesting events to report on and exciting new ventures ahead. I am really grateful to the many active members of the DDI community who continue to make contributions and to give generously of their time. Our success is due to your tireless efforts.

Mary Vardigan, Director, DDI Alliance

New DDI Alliance Officers Elected

The DDI Alliance is pleased to announce that Chuck Humphrey (Chair), University of Alberta, and Mari Kleemola (Vice Chair), Finnish Social Science Data Archive, have been elected to lead the DDI Expert Committee, beginning January 1, 2010.

Chuck has been the Head of the Data Library at the University of Alberta since 1992 and also assumed responsibility for the

Jannik Jensen, DDA, demonstrates his DDI editor at the European Users Group Meeting in Bonn.

Chuck Humphrey

Mari Kleemola

implementation and management of a Statistics Canada Research Data Centre (RDC) at the University of Alberta in 2001. Mari is Information Services Manager at the Finnish Social Science Data Archive (FSD) in the

areas of User Services, Data Processing, and Documentation.

Congratulations, Chuck and Mari, and thank you for being willing to serve in this capacity. We look forward to a productive year ahead!

DDI Alliance Expert Committee to Meet in Ithaca, NY

On Monday, May 31, 2010, the Expert Committee of the DDI Alliance will meet in Ithaca, NY, just before the start of the [IASSIST meeting](#), which runs June 1-4. More details will be available early in 2010.

DDI Training and Conferences Continue

During the period October through December, DDI was again on the road to spread the word about the standard.

Training was held in October Australia for the [Australian Social Science Data Archive \(ASSDA\)](#) and for the [Australian Bureau of Statistics \(ABS\)](#). As a result of the meetings at ABS,

From left, Peter Granda, ICPSR; Joachim Wackerow, GESIS; Wendy Thomas, University of Minnesota; and Geoff Lee, Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS), following a presentation at ABS in October.

the Bureau is exploring a strategy for implementing both DDI and [SDMX](#).

In early November after DDI 3 training was conducted at [Schloss Dagstuhl](#) near

Wadern, Germany, an [Expert Workshop on DDI Use Cases](#) was held. The participants wrote first drafts of nine papers illustrating key DDI 3 use cases. These papers will be published early in 2010, resulting in a use case literature to guide others in implementing DDI.

DDI was an important theme at the [CESSDA Expert Seminar](#) held in November in Ljubljana, Slovenia, with the focus “Towards the CESSDA-ERIC metadata model and DDI3.” Representatives from the CESSDA archives in Europe discussed their usage of DDI and their views on its potential for the future.

An “EduDDI” training was held in Bamberg, Germany, in November with participants from five German institutes

Joachim Wackerow, GESIS, conducts DDI 3 training in Bamberg, Germany.

from the domain of educational research and testing:

- [NEPS/INBIL \(Institute for Educational Research Bamberg\)](#)
- [DIPF \(Leibniz Institute for Educational Research and Educational Information\)](#)
- [TestDaF \(German as a foreign language\)](#)
- [IEA-DPC \(Data Processing and Research Center at the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement\)](#)
- [IQB \(Institute for Educational Progress\)](#)

European DDI Users Group (EDDI) Meeting Takes Place

The [First Annual European DDI Users Group Meeting](#) on

the topic “DDI - The Basis of Managing the Data Life Cycle” took place at the [International Data Service Center \(IDSC\)](#) of the [Institute for the Study of Labor \(IZA\)](#) in Bonn, Germany, on December 4 with 60 participants from 10 countries attending and 35 participating in training on December 3. The [program](#) offered 14 presentations highlighting different areas of DDI interest.

The Opening Plenary was given by [Kevin Schürer](#), Director of the [Economic and Social Data Service \(ESDS\)](#) and the [UK Data Archive \(UKDA\)](#) on the topic “Why DDI must succeed and the perils of it not doing so.”

The EDDI organizers were Nikos Askitas (IZA), Joachim Wackerow ([GESIS–Leibniz](#)

[Institute for the Social Sciences](#)), and Georgios Tassoukis (IZA). Many thanks to the organizers for a successful meeting.

EDDI 2010 will take place December 4, 2010, at Tilburg University in the Netherlands, with support from a group of four institutions: [Library and IT Services at Tilburg University](#), [DANS](#), [SURF](#), and [CentERdata](#).

New Members Join the Alliance

The DDI Alliance welcomed three new members into membership recently:

- [Australian Social Science Data Archive \(ASSDA\)](#), with Dr. Steven McEachern as the Expert Committee representative
- [University of Toronto Scholars Portal](#), with Leanne Hindmarch as the Expert Committee representative
- [Research Data Centre of the German Federal Employment Agency, Institute for Employment Research \(IAB\)](#), with Stefan Bender as the Expert Committee representative

Welcome to all! We look forward to meeting with you in 2010.

Participants in the 2009 Dagstuhl Use Case Workshop

DDI Editing Framework Released

Jannik Jensen, a software developer at the Danish Data Archive (DDA), has released parts of a DDI editing framework as open source software. The release was announced at the European DDI users group meeting in Bonn.

The DDI editing framework is being developed as part of the DDI Foundation Tools Program:

<http://tools.ddialliance.org/>

The modules and project information can be found at the [DDI Editing Framework Web site](#).

DDI Web Site Revised

A new version of the [DDI Web site](#) based on the content management system Drupal will go live early in 2010. The site offers revised navigation and some new features, including a DDI calendar, a DDI timeline, and other new content. Drupal enables multiple people to edit and add content to the site.

Currently, the site is maintained by the DDI Usability and Outreach Group consisting of Michelle Edwards, Stefan Kramer, Kate McNeill, Ron Nakao, and Mary Vardigan. If you would like to contribute to building and maintaining the site, please contact the [UOG chairs, Stefan Kramer and Kate McNeill](#).

The Deutsche Post Tower in Bonn, site of the European DDI Users Group meeting (EDDI) in December.

Sign welcoming participants to the first annual EDDI meeting.